

“Sustainability assessment of the CO₂ methanation value chain: environmental impacts and socio-economic drivers and barriers”

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Final Scientific Report (subproject)

A. Summary

Lead

Within this project the sustainability assessment of the CO₂ methanation value chain was performed by analyzing the following four technologies: catalytic methanation, hydrogen production with Photo-Electrochemical Cells (PEC), Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) fuel cells, and Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC).

Background

Energy efficiency with respect to resource and climate conservation is one of the most challenging and urgent problems of our time. But as large and important as these targets are, they will not be adopted by the public as long as they are not cost-effective, lifestyle-compatible and environmentally friendly throughout the value chain. That is why we opted to evaluate new approaches for generating electricity along the CO₂ methanation value chain with reference to all these perspectives, and to consider their results not only in public policy-making, but also for strategic decisions in companies.

Aim

The goal of this research project was to assess the whole CO₂ methanation value chain regarding social, economic and environmental sustainability by comparing various scenarios from cradle to grave.

Results

The results for the environmental sustainability depend substantially on the type of electricity used for the hydrogen production. The researchers identified a significant potential to reduce life cycle greenhouse gas emissions, when comparing renewable and fossil methane value chains **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** The reason for this reduction potential is the fact that the combustion of fossil methane releases carbon dioxide emissions that contribute to global warming whereas the direct carbon dioxide emissions from the combustion of synthetic methane are equal to the carbon dioxide amount used as input in the methanation process and therefore are climate neutral. The economic investigation dealt with the calculation of the possible investment and operating costs in comparison to the currently found base scenario. In summary, it can be said that there are ways to break away from the dependency of fossil natural gas to produce self-sufficient renewable methane within Switzerland. With improvements in efficiencies, increased transit and operating times, the use of energy flows below process steps, and increased maintenance intervals, especially new technologies, there are many ways to minimize the cost difference. More accurate statements require more thorough detailed investigations. On the social dimension, it can be said that the processes involved in the subprojects are not of more concern than normal Swiss industrial activities. However, attention must be paid at the provenance of bulk materials, especially of metals (copper) and conflict minerals, cassiterite (tin), wolframite (for tungsten), coltan (for tantalum), and gold ore. For the assessed subprojects the critical materials are usually the catalysts (nickel or metals of the platinum group). It was discovered that the supply chains are usually untraceable, making it impossible to trace the exact provenance location and their respective social conditions. A strategy to fight this issue is for the Swiss companies to demand more transparency for the purchased bulk materials.

Implication for research

The findings of this research project revealed the social, economic and environmental hotspots of the whole CO₂ methanation value chain, which can be used by the researchers in the single subprojects and later by the implementing industry to improve the sustainability of their end-products.

Implication for practice

The findings and recommendations of this research project are important for decision making in policy with regard to the energy strategy 2050 and for industries to improve their sustainability performances, e.g. by reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

B. Objectives of the research project in relation to Energy Strategy 2050

The Swiss “Energy Strategy 2050” emphasises – among other points – the promotion of increased renewable energies to contribute to a more sustainable energy system (Swiss Federal Council, 2011). Hydrogen could well become the major component of clean sustainable energy systems in the longer term. It is relevant to all energy sectors – transportation, buildings, utilities, and industry. Hydrogen converted into methane can provide storage options for intermittent renewable technologies such as solar and wind, and methanising carbon dioxide and hydrogen can substantially reduce greenhouse gas emissions from the cement industry, but potentially also from gas and steam co-generation plants as well as biomass reactors. The application of mobile fuel cells in the transport sector is a promising approach for greenhouse gas mitigation. Furthermore, the stationary fuel cell technology (SOFC) as a combined heat and power supply source for single family houses also contributes by saving primary energy carriers due to their high conversion efficiency. The aim of the “Energy Strategy 2050” is to initiate a switch from a system of subsidising renewable energies to a more incentive-based steering system. In order to guide this changing nature of hydrogen production in a sustainable way, thanks to the SNF funding we were able to provide insights into the environmental, social and economic impact assessments of photoelectrochemical (PEC) hydrogen production and the carbon dioxide methanation value chain.

C. Main results attained

The umbrella project “CO₂ Reduction & Reuse – Renewable Fuels for Efficient Electricity Production” consists of four technical subprojects that serve different purposes (for instance home heating or driving a car) and one project that analyses the sustainability impacts of the involved technologies. In order to present results that can be compared with current competing technologies, scenarios were defined according to the energy utilisation path.

Three paths were defined (Methane to gas network, home heating and hydrogen car) with five scenarios each. Depicted on Figure 1 are the four technical subprojects: Photoelectrochemical water splitting (PEC), Proton exchange membrane (PEM), Methanation, and Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC).

Figure 1: Summary of scenarios of energy utilization of subprojects (PEC, PEM, Methanation and SOFC) and their competing technologies according to their respective path: methane to gas network, methane for home heating or hydrogen for cars.

The five scenarios were defined to describe the fossil-based status quo (Base Scenario), a scenario with hydrogen from PEC and scenarios with hydrogen from catalytic electrolysis using different power technologies: photovoltaic power (Scenario 2), surplus power (Scenario 3A) and normal Swiss grid power (Scenario 3B).

First, the results for the different scenarios and paths from the three different sustainability perspectives are presented. Afterwards an overview that combines the three perspectives (by means of a multi-criteria decision analysis) is given. Lastly, a SWOT analysis is provided.

Environmental

The results for the environmental sustainability depend substantially on the type of electricity used for the hydrogen production. The researchers identified a significant potential to reduce life cycle greenhouse gas emissions, when comparing renewable and fossil methane value chains (see Figure 2 **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**). The reason for this reduction potential is the fact that the combustion of fossil methane releases carbon dioxide emissions that contribute to global warming whereas the direct carbon dioxide emissions from the combustion of synthetic methane are equal to the carbon dioxide amount used as input in the methanation process and therefore are climate neutral. However, these climate protection gains may come at the cost of other negative impacts, such as radioactive wastes, if current grid electricity is used for hydrogen production. Therefore, for a positive environmental evaluation, it is essential that the development of renewable methanation value chains in Switzerland comes hand in hand with the change to a renewable electricity in the country. If hydrogen is produced with surplus or low impact renewable energy, methanation value chains have a potential for environmental sustainability. The scenarios will go different development trends, which is illustrated by the arrows in Figure 2. Greenhouse gas emissions of the base scenario will increase, due to the increasing scarcity of raw materials and the resulting more complex extraction technologies. In scenario 1 and scenario 2, greenhouse gas emissions will decrease as a result of improved PV and PEC technology. Assuming a future improvement in power-to-gas technology too, also in scenario 3A and scenario 3B greenhouse gas emissions will decrease, although less than in scenario 1 and scenario 2.

Figure 2: Greenhouse gas emissions in kg CO₂-eq. per m³ methane from power-to-gas production with various electricity sources and hydrogen production methodologies (scenario 1–3B) and feeding into the natural gas network compared to fossil natural gas (base scenario, including combustion emissions). The arrows indicate the future development trends of the scenarios.

Economic

The economic investigation dealt with the calculation of the possible investment and operating costs in comparison to the currently found base scenario. The starting point of the calculations was the annual carbon dioxide output of Swiss cement plants. Costs and efficiencies of established technologies are known and have been scaled in view of the expected plant sizes (photovoltaic, alkaline electrolysis). Other technologies have been tested, but have not yet been used on a large scale (SOFC, methanation, hydrogen car). The operating costs can be specified in these cases only with a certain probability. Photo-electrochemical cells are currently still in the laboratory stage. Cost and efficiencies are the hardest to estimate in this case. The advantage of new technologies is the potential for development. The results for path 1 (methane to gas network) show that the baseline scenario is the most cost effective method of using natural gas or methane (659 million CHF/a). Fossil gas can be sourced almost indefinitely at a very reasonable price from abroad. Investment costs are negligible in this case, as the infrastructure already exists in Switzerland. All other technologies are associated with investments in the tens of billions CHF. In second position follows scenario 3B with 4 times the costs per year. Scenarios 2 and 3A require 6 times the cost of the baseline scenario. Scenario 1 is the first alternative to methane production in this comparison with 8 times the cost. It should be noted that scenario 1, 2 and 3A only produce renewable methane.

Figure 3: Opex costs path 1 - methane to gas network

Path 2 (home heating) is supplemented by only the consumer compared to path 1, therefore the order does not change. Path 3 compares the cost of hydrogen production. Again, the same order as in path 1, where the costs are closer together compared to the baseline scenario.

Figure 4: Opex costs path 3 - hydrogen production (included gas stations)

The costs for hydrogen production including the filling station network amount to: 1927 million CHF/a (base), 5576 million CHF/a (scenario 1), 4108 million CHF/a (scenario 2), 4212 million CHF/a (scenario 3A), 2989 million CHF/a (scenario 3B). The cost of the hydrogen vehicles are not shown in the graph. It is assumed that a switch to hydrogen vehicles of this size (over 3 million cars) will not cause further costs.

In summary, it can be said that there are ways to break away from the dependency of fossil natural gas to produce self-sufficient renewable methane within Switzerland. For the provision of energy by sunlight (PV + PEC), Switzerland is not optimally suited (1200 full load hours per year). With improvements in efficiencies, increased transit and operating times, the use of energy flows below process steps, and increased maintenance intervals, especially new technologies, there are many ways to minimize the cost difference. More accurate statements require more thorough and detailed investigations.

Social

The approach we used to assess the social conditions was to answer following questions: Firstly, “where are the materials most likely to be sourced and processed?” and “how are the social conditions in the respective sectors of those countries (so-called country-sectors)?”. Since the provenance of bulk materials was mostly unknown to the project partners and impossible for us to trace, the first question was answered mainly with statistical data (e.g. CIA’s World Factbook, U.S. Geological Survey, among others). To describe the social conditions of the country-sectors, on a first instance, the social hotspots database was applied and further deepened with customized desktop research. However, the complexity of the value chain, the inability to trace certain product/material to its origins, and the rapidly changing social conditions make it impossible to accurately assess the social impact of a specific product. For example, if there is copper in a product it is very difficult to find out if the metal comes from a socially responsible mine in Chile or an artisanal mine in the Democratic Republic of Congo with poor social conditions. Therefore, the results have to be understood merely in an informative manner and as guidance for socially responsible manufacturing of these technologies.

On a general note, it can be said that the processes involved in the subprojects are not of more concern than normal Swiss industrial activities. However, attention must be paid at the provenance of bulk materials, especially of metals (copper) and conflict minerals, cassiterite (tin), wolframite (for tungsten), coltan (for tantalum), and gold ore. For the assessed subprojects the critical materials are usually the catalysts (nickel or metals of the platinum group). It was discovered that the supply chains are usually untraceable, making it impossible to trace the exact provenance location and their respective social conditions. A strategy to fight this issue is for the Swiss companies to demand more transparency for the purchased bulk materials and to engage in non-governmental initiatives, who collaborate with the mining industries for a responsible mineral sourcing.

Multi Criteria Decision Analysis

The multi-criteria decision analysis attempts to bring together the three sustainability perspectives and to aggregate them into a combined result. It is worth to consider that the methodologies used on each perspective are different and not always compatible. However, some interesting conclusions can be observed.

For methane to gas network, the base scenario has the lowest sustainability mark (cf. fig. 5; 1 unit per perspective, the other scenarios are normalized to this value). Apart from base scenario, scenario 3A (methane, produced with hydrogen production supplied by surplus power, fed into the natural gas network) has the lowest sustainability mark. In the environmental perspective, it was considered that surplus power does not cause any impact. On the other hand, if hydrogen were produced with current Swiss power (Scenario 3B) the impact would be higher. This because of the high ratio of nuclear power in the Swiss grid mix, which

generates radioactive waste, and is associated with high environmental impacts according to the Ecological Scarcity Method (2013).

On the social perspective, the risk of social issues increases because the base case reflects the social situation from fossil methane produced mainly in the EU and Russia, which has a lower risk than the sourcing of minerals (mostly nickel in Indonesia). Compared to the other scenarios, scenario 3A, in which hydrogen production is supplied by surplus electricity, has the lowest environmental impacts, but CO₂ capturing costs and operation costs are high, resulting in a higher sustainability mark than scenario 3B. Scenario 1, in which hydrogen production is supplied by PEC power plant, has the highest sustainability mark due to high costs for CO₂ capturing and operation, as well as high environmental impacts caused by metal consumption during PEC cell production for hydrogen production.

Figure 5: Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis, all values normalised to the base scenario. Base scenario on every path has a value of three (dimensionless units), one unit per each sustainability perspective. For social and economic no weighting was assigned (each parameter bears 0.25 units), for environmental, the values are already weighted by the ecological scarcity method 2013.

The sustainability mark for home heating is the lowest for the base case. Worth to note is that the most striking differences are on the economic side, where all scenarios perform poorly in comparison to the base scenario. This is not surprising since the technologies for the base scenario require little or no investment. However, compared to the base scenario, the efforts yield a better performance in term of global warming impact. Nevertheless, other environmental impacts arise (scenario 1 and scenario 3B) mainly because of the heavy metal emissions into water due to the PEC cell production and the deposition of nuclear waste due to the consumption of Swiss grid mix for hydrogen production. The social performance for all scenarios remains in a comparable range, with the power to gas technologies presenting the best grade due to the electricity production in Europe.

In the case for driving with hydrogen-powered PEM fuel cell cars, the sustainability mark is the lowest for scenario 3A and highest for scenario 1. This because the investment for all cases is comparable. In the case of scenario 1, the mark is slightly higher because of the PEC investments. On the ecological perspective, the results are lowest, if surplus electricity or electricity with low environmental impact is used for hydrogen production. On the social perspective, scenario 1 bears the burden from the catalyst used for the PEC and the marks are lowest for the base case where electricity is produced in Europe.

SWOT analysis

Methane Path

	Positive	Negative
Internal	<p>Strengths</p> <p>The infrastructure for storage and commercialization of product (Methane) already exists.</p> <p>The use of PtG methane reduces greenhouse gas emissions compared to the use of fossil methane.</p> <p>CO₂ from waste gases, such as from cement plants, is currently unused and sufficiently available for the conversion into methane.</p>	<p>Weaknesses</p> <p>The electrolysis with electricity from the current Swiss grid mix includes a high ratio of nuclear power, which is associated with nuclear waste that needs to be disposed and stored for very long time periods.</p> <p>PEC technology is still on a laboratory scale and not yet in industrial use. Up-scaling to industrial production involves uncertainties in terms of service life, production volume and infrastructure.</p>
External	<p>Opportunities</p> <p>Synthetic methane can be produced with renewable local power.</p> <p>The production of PtG methane reduces the Swiss dependency from the global market of fossil fuels.</p> <p>If hydrogen for PtG methane can be produced with surplus or low impact renewable energy, overall environmental impacts are lower compared to fossil fuel.</p> <p>The environmental impact of the Swiss grid mix decreases with the energy strategy 2050, which will improve the environmental performance of synthetic methane.</p> <p>The background electricity mix, e.g. for producing photovoltaic technology may also improve in future, which will result in lower environmental impacts of synthetic methane produced with photovoltaic electricity.</p>	<p>Threat</p> <p>In order to convert all CO₂ emissions from the cement industry in Switzerland into methane using hydrogen produced with solar energy, an enormous module area would be required.</p> <p>Not enough surplus electricity is currently available in Switzerland, to supply methanation value chains.</p>

Hydrogen Path

	Positive	Negative
Internal	<p>Strenghts</p> <p>High quality product with multiple applications.</p> <p>The direct use of renewable hydrogen in PEM fuel cell cars is more efficient than its further conversion to methane.</p> <p>Renewable hydrogen reduces the environmental impacts, if surplus or low impact renewable energy is used for its production.</p>	<p>Weaknesses</p> <p>The infrastructure to store (tanks) and commercialize (service stations) hydrogen does not yet exist in Switzerland and would have to be expanded first, in order to enable driving with fuel cell cars.</p>
External	<p>Opportunities</p> <p>With PEM fuel cell cars the demand for the product rises.</p> <p>With further technology maturity, PEM fuel cell production will be more material and energy efficient, resulting in lower environmental impacts.</p>	<p>Threats</p> <p>Price of competitor (oil) at the moment too low, but volatile.</p>

D. Please outline the contribution of your project to the key questions of NRP 70

1) What new knowledge has been created and how is this knowledge gain contributing towards the successful implementation of Energy Strategy 2050?

The environmental, social and economic evaluation of the whole CO₂ methanation value chain identified the most important hotspots, uncovered potential for improvement and made recommendations for the successful implementation of the Energy Strategy 2050.

The environmental assessment revealed, that the electricity source for hydrogen production is the crucial factor concerning power-to-gas (PtG) technology and that surplus or low impact energy is essential to make the CO₂ methanation value chain competitive with fossil fuels. The environmental competitiveness of PtG technology is also linked to the change to renewable electricity in Switzerland. Compared to fossil methane value chains, renewable methane value chains using power to gas technology have a significant potential to reduce life cycle greenhouse gas emissions and therefore contribute to the Swiss climate policy targets.

2) Which groups are the findings targeted at and which principal actors are indispensable in terms of practical implementation?

The findings of this project are addressed to policymakers to help them make the right decisions for the Energy Strategy 2050. The results are also addressed to scientists and technology developers who make individual links in the CO₂ methanation value chain more sustainable and thus make the entire CO₂ methanation value chain a powerful measure for more greenhouse gas mitigation in Switzerland.

3) What are the potential opportunities and threats when it comes to transitioning findings, achieving readiness for application and preparing roll-out?

The current economic results base on today's system costs in low scale implementation. Although certain upscaling effects are considered, unexpected benefits from large-scale implementation are possible. The modest solar conditions of Switzerland for efficient energy harvesting have to be mentioned. This results in very low peak operation hours over the year and thus to high investment costs. An outsourcing of the solar energy harvesting to countries with better irradiation (e.g. Southern Italy, Spain, or North Africa) would probably halve the investment costs. Nevertheless, the costs for capturing one tonne of CO₂ by sustainable methanation are far beyond any sufficiency measures that avoid primary emissions of CO₂. The above scenarios 1 and 2 result in capturing costs of around 1000.- CHF per tonne of CO₂. Comparing this magnitude of order with today's less than 30.- CHF offered for the compensation of one tonne by myClimate.org the question arises what the real price would be? From an economic point of view, CO₂ methanation will make sense after the low hanging fruits for CO₂ emission reduction are put into practice.

Results of the environmental assessment (using the ecological scarcity method with aggregation of eco-points) for the defined scenarios along the CO₂ methanation value chain highlight that power-to-gas brings reduction in greenhouse gas emissions. Total environmental impacts are less in scenario 3a (especially when using surplus electricity for methanation). However, the impacts caused by using batteries and emerging technologies but also assumptions of upscale need to be taken into consideration as well. The base scenario and scenario 2 (thin film PV out of Cd-Te & methanation) are more or less in the same range. Nevertheless, there is still room for improvement with need for further research (a trend of 20% reduction in scenario 2 within the next 10 years explains the reduction potential in "heavy metals into air"). SOFC fuel cell for home heating reduce impacts compared to conventional heating. Additional benefit from renewable methane is small. Scenarios for methane in PEM fuel cell car produce again positive results (50% greenhouse gas emissions of petrol-driven cars). Compared to fossil methane, synthetic methane reduces the emission of climate-damaging greenhouse gas emissions. Looking at total environmental impacts, synthetic methane can compete with fossil methane, if hydrogen is produced with surplus energy, PV or 2035 electricity mix. The results depend significantly on the type of electricity for the hydrogen production.

The faced challenges in the analysis of the social impacts of certain technologies showed different scopes of action: development of practicable methods and tools to assess social compatibility of products and technologies, higher transparency of value chains and the establishment of some sort of fair-trade label for minerals. Due to those problems, no quantitative results could be gathered in the social impact analysis. Because of that, there is a certain risk that results are not taken as reliable and thus not as important as "hard facts" of e.g. an environmental assessment. However, we can hold on that we should pay special attention when using minerals that are potential conflict minerals (3 T and Gold). But mining in general imposes a high risk for social incompatibility. If a label of fair-mined products will be established in the future, the labelled product can attract new customers, which are willing to pay more for this additional value. There is a trend for reducing material demand especially regarding palladium and minerals from the platinum group, this will also have a positive effect on the social impact of the technologies, even if it was maybe more financially motivated. An important aspect in sustainability assessment is to address also negative (or positive) side effects, which are maybe out of the system boundaries. In our case for example the need for smarter cars and home control systems, which need more electrical devices, that lead again to a higher resource demand. In the Multi Criteria Decision Analysis, with the normalization referred to the base case, the path hydrogen car resulted in much better social conditions (if electricity is produced in Europe).

In this project, a methodology to assess social impacts of a value chain in comparison to the situation in Switzerland has been established. A social compass for priority setting is proposed comparing to Swiss status-quo with performance reference points: In general, the social conditions are not worse than normal industrial activities, however attention need to be payed to catalysts and conflict minerals. Unfortunately, supply chains are (often) untraceable, transparency (through Fairmined label e.g. for gold) could be increased but will make it more expensive. Therefore, only a reduced social focus could be developed for later aggregation with the other sustainability dimensions. Nevertheless, this method could be further elaborated and tested in practice, which could raise awareness for social responsibility and its importance in companies.

4) What is the technological readiness level¹⁾ of the envisaged end product(s) at the start and at the conclusion of this research project?

No product was actually developed.

5) What trade-offs (environmental impact, grey energy etc.) does broad practical application of the findings entail?

If hydrogen for the CO₂ methanation value chain is produced with current grid electricity, the sustainability performance is dominated by the nuclear waste related to the power generation or even an increase of electricity imports from fossil power plants abroad.

The significant potential of CO₂ methanation value chains to reduce greenhouse gas emissions compared to fossil methane is in a trade-off to other environmental impacts such as land use for solar technology or air pollution and to social aspects related to the production of the various metals used in the value chain.

6) How cost-efficient (measured over a complete life cycle) is broad practical application of the findings?

Unexpected benefits of large-scale implementation are possible. The environmental assessment revealed, that the electricity source for hydrogen production is the crucial factor concerning power-to-gas (PtG) technology and that surplus or low impact energy is essential to make the CO₂ methanation value chain competitive with fossil fuels. A cost estimation for CO₂ reduction and reuse by methanation from cement industry sources in Switzerland is provided in Baier et al. (2018).

7) Which incentive mechanisms/support measures are necessary to ensure rapid and broad application of the findings?

To support more climate friendly technology systems and make them financially more attractive compared to fossil-based technologies respective incentives for the acquisition of low-carbon and/or a CO₂-tax for fossil-based technologies could be a suitable policy instrument. To reduce primary mineral extraction, which has a high risk for social incompatibility and is a rising cost factor too, recycling of metals could be promoted and financially supported.

1) *Technological readiness levels A to D:*

Level A: Concept (corresponds to TRL 1 - 3)

Level B: Validation (corresponds to TRL 4 - 5)

Level C: Prototyping (corresponds to TRL 6 - 7)

Level D: Roll-out (corresponds to TRL 8 - 9)

(TRL 1 - 9: Technology readiness levels as defined by the US Department of Energy, 2008 / Swiss Federal Office of Energy)

E. Point out the findings of your project that are relevant to the thematic synthesis of NRP 70 and NRP 71

1) Building and Settlement

Both, SOFC & PEM fuel cells are high efficiency decentralised devices bringing CO₂ savings for domestic area. With the introduction of more renewables gas (e.g. SNG or biogas) for SOFCs, this technology becomes CO₂ neutral. It can easily be applied in buildings, which account for about 40% of total energy consumption. Additionally, SOFC technology can serve as a sector coupling technology by combining the electricity and gas grid.

2) Hydropower and Market

n/a

3) Energy Infrastructures

Renewable methane causes lower greenhouse gas emissions than fossil methane. However, these climate protection gains may come at the cost of other negative impacts, such as radioactive wastes, if current grid electricity is used for hydrogen production. The joint project under consideration contributes largely with its concept and valorisation chain to the so-called sector coupling from electricity, gas and heat networks of Switzerland. A realistic costs scenario for the replacement of 1/3 of the fossil gas imports, which derives from converting all available CO₂ emissions from the 6 cement plants in Switzerland has been elaborated.

4) Market Conditions and Regulation

There are ways to break away from the dependency of fossil natural gas to produce self-sufficient renewable methane within Switzerland. For the provision of energy by sunlight (PV + PEC), Switzerland is not optimally suited (1200 full load hours per year). With improvements in efficiencies, increased transit and operating times, the use of energy flows below process steps, and increased maintenance intervals, especially new technologies, there are many ways to minimize the cost difference. More accurate statements require more thorough and detailed investigations. Beside an ecological life-cycle assessment, sustainability and social impacts are evaluated deriving from our value chain.

5) Acceptance

It was discovered that the supply chains are usually untraceable, making it impossible to trace the exact provenance location and their respective social conditions. A strategy to fight this issue is for the Swiss companies to demand more transparency for the purchased bulk materials and to engage in non-governmental initiatives, who collaborate with the mining industries for a responsible mineral sourcing. Higher transparency of value chains and the establishment of some sort of fair-trade label for minerals may increase acceptance of the CO₂ methanation value chain.

6) Mobility Behaviour

n/a. The direct use of renewable hydrogen in PEM fuel cell cars is more efficient than its further conversion to methane.

7) Transformation and Innovation

Technologies analysed in this project have been tested, but have not yet been used on a large scale (SOFC, methanation, hydrogen car). The operating costs can be specified in these cases only with a certain probability. Photo-electrochemical cells are currently still in the laboratory stage. Cost and efficiencies are the hardest to estimate in this case. The advantage of all these new technologies is the potential for development. Sufficiency is crucial beside efficiency in the transformation of the energy system. Three out of four concepts do provide technologies for reaching higher efficiency but also provide a positive sufficiency effect.

F. Three main messages

Please state briefly three main messages you can deduce from the results of your research with regard to the transformation of the energy system in Switzerland.

- 1)** The results of the environmental sustainability of the CO₂ methanation value chain depend substantially on the type of electricity used for hydrogen production, which leads to a significant potential to reduce life cycle greenhouse gas emissions when renewable instead of fossil energy is used for hydrogen production.
- 2)** For a positive environmental evaluation, it is essential that the development of renewable methanation value chains in Switzerland comes hand in hand with the change to a renewable electricity in the country.
- 3)** All analysed scenarios have two additional sustainability challenges compared to the state of the art (fossil methane): They have to become financially attractive and production must be socially responsible (especially concerning mining activities). This needs ongoing efforts of technology developers and innovative companies.

G. Implications and recommendations

Which implications for practice and science do directly result from your research? Recommendations for policy makers and experts from the practical realm should also be provided in this section. There has to be a clear link between the recommendations and the results from which they are derived.

1) Scientific implications

There is further need for research for upscale considerations by using batteries and emerging technologies with regards to sustainability impacts assessment. In this project, a methodology to assess social impacts of a value chain in comparison to the situation in Switzerland has been further developed. However, further implementations in practice need to be tested, which could raise awareness for social responsibility and its importance in companies.

2) Policy recommendations

To promote the CO₂ methanation value chains, the Swiss electricity mix would have to become more sustainable in the future and consist of a higher portion of low impact renewable sources. Only if hydrogen is produced with surplus or very low impact renewable energy, methanation value chains have a potential for environmental sustainability.

A legal requirement for transparency of purchased materials (origin and processing) should be established in order to enable social impacts assessment and improvements in value chains of products. Urban mining processes should be established, promoted and financially supported. Social life cycle assessment should be further elaborated and tools for practical use in Swiss companies should be developed. Especially data analysis on social impacts of specific metals should be improved.

Capturing CO₂ after it has been emitted will always be far less economic than avoiding the emission. Therefore, the political focus should be put on aggressive reduction of conventional fossil fuel use. The main emitters should be addressed first: Home heating (insulation, alternative energy harvesting, reduction of living space per person), transport (alternative fuels (e.g. hydrogen, electricity), much higher fossil fuel tax, shift to public transport, reduction in km per person, proper fuel tax on air travel), waste treatment (upscale recycling, reduce packaging in consumer products), etc.

H. Knowledge and technology transfer (KTT)

Max 2'500 characters.

1) What target groups have you worked with and what are the results of this cooperation?

For gathering social datasets, we interviewed NGOs active in this field, most notably with Public Eye (former Erklärung von Bern). Our social research was also handled with students at the Bachelor and Master level (e.g. Case Studies on Conflict Minerals within the Module on Future-Oriented Technology Assessment) resulting in increased awareness of future engineers. Relevant industries such as Hexis and Holcim have been informed about the outcomes of the research generating mutual knowledge exchange. Further knowledge transfer to CEM-Suisse is planned to explore future dissemination and exploitation opportunities.

2) All the completed KTT products, activities and measures need to be listed as "Output data" in "mySNF". Which of all your products/activities do you consider as the three most relevant ones in terms of content and knowledge transfer?

Products/activities	Target group(s)	Expected impact
1. Baier J, Schneider G and Heel A (2018) "A Cost Estimation for CO ₂ Reduction and Re-use by Methanation from Cement Industry Sources in Switzerland". <i>Front. Energy Res.</i> 6:5. doi: 10.3389/fenrg.2018.00005	The article is an open access publication accessible to readers anywhere in the world	Raising awareness of the potential and challenges for large scale implementation of methanation technologies from a economic point of view.
2. Wettstein, Sarah and Stucki, Matthias (2017). Synthetic Power-to-Gas Methane as Fuel for Transportation - Life Cycle Environmental Impacts of the PtG Methane Supply Chain Powered by Renewable Electricity: Oral presentation. In: Life Cycle Management 2017. Conference (4. September 2017). Luxemburg: Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology LIST.	Scientists and industry partners in the fields of PtG technology and automotive industry.	Raising awareness of the ecological advantages of the methane value chain and its future opportunities in the automotive industry.
3. Lobsiger-Kägi, Evelyn; Lopez, Luis; Kuehn, Tobias; Roth, Raoul; Carabias, Vicente; Zipper, Christian. "An Efficient Method for Social Life Cycle Assessments Based On Relevance Analysis and the Use of Performance Reference Points for Switzerland", in preparation for submission.	Scientists in the field of Social and Sustainability Life Cycle Assessment	Contribution to the discussion and development of SLCA methods Raising awareness for Social LCA and its challenges.

3) Future implementation and knowledge transfer activities:

Are implementation and/or knowledge transfer activities planned after the submission of this report and after the conclusion of this project respectively?

The knowledge and expertise gained in this project will be applied in other research projects on sustainability assessment and transferred into teaching, dissemination and exploitation.

Annexe

Brief outline of the key topics addressed by the thematic synthesis reports

The objective of the thematic synthesis reports is to incorporate the findings of thematically related research projects under NRP 70 and 71 to produce new, overarching insights. Recommendations for action are to be drawn up based on the underlying research.

The thematic synthesis reports on the following seven topics are planned (decision of the National Research Council of 8 August 2017):

Building and settlement

Accounting for around 40% of total energy requirements, building and settlement play a key role in terms of energy efficiency and the decentralised exploitation of new renewable energy sources. Several projects under the mantle of NRP 70 and 71 explore the associated challenges from both a technical and a socio-political standpoint. The research findings span the topics of high-performance photovoltaics and its integration into building envelopes; technical, organisational and economic concepts for the decentralised supply of energy to residential settlements; novel storage technologies; and far-reaching changes in living patterns and behaviour. A further aim of this synthesis report is to examine the topics of compact urban settlement and the health risks posed by high-density construction.

Hydropower and market

Hydropower is by far the biggest source of renewable energy in Switzerland. Hence, it faces tough competition from new renewable energy sources such as solar power, wind and biomass, especially given that these are all heavily subsidised at present. Key issues here are the viable contribution that hydropower can make to transforming our energy system, as well as the systemic integration of hydropower into the Swiss energy landscape. A number of research projects under NRP 70 and 71 are examining the widely differing technical and economic aspects of future hydropower exploitation. The objective of this synthesis report is to collate and combine the findings of these research activities and to put forward recommendations for the further development of hydropower in Switzerland.

Energy infrastructures

This key topic incorporates the research projects under NRP 70 and 71 that are looking into the general technical, ecological and social conditions shaping new, innovative energy infrastructures as well as into the drivers and obstacles. Installations to exploit geothermal energy, hydropower and wind energy are the main area of interest, along with energy distribution networks (electricity, gas, heat) and alternative bulk storage systems, such as compressed air or thermal energy tanks. The focus of this synthesis report is on technical feasibility, cost effectiveness and spatial impact. The latter is not narrowly restricted to land use, but also includes the numerous aspects of landscape and biodiversity.

Market conditions and regulation

The objective of this synthesis report on market conditions and regulation is to pool and incorporate relevant findings from the economics-focused research projects of NRP 70 and 71. In particular, the report will outline the expected consequences of a promotion and a steering-based

energy policy and of an ecological tax reform in terms of innovation, efficiency and distribution. It will also show how the energy market could be optimally regulated with due regard to efficiency and distribution.

Acceptance

To ensure the success of the impending fundamental transformation of our energy system, effective strategies have to be found that meet with majority support from society and at local level. Seen in this context, numerous projects under the aegis of NRP 70 and 71 directly or indirectly address questions of acceptance, i.e., typically, acceptance of the risks associated with energy supply (e.g. geothermal energy), acceptance of locations for electric power generation or transmission, or acceptance of behavioural measures (e.g. information campaigns, nudges). The remit of the synthesis report on acceptance is to incorporate and amalgamate the findings of these projects.

Mobility behaviour

The past has shown that the control of energy consumption in the transport sector is more difficult than in other areas. Attention has therefore been focused under NRP 71 on questions of mobility behaviour and its impact on energy consumption. The objective of this thematic synthesis report is to incorporate the findings of NRP 71 projects tackling issues of mobility, in particular mobility behaviour. Technical innovations such as electromobility, autonomous vehicles and traffic management have not been addressed under NRP 70 and 71. The remit of this synthesis report is, as far as possible, also to include existing research findings from the Swiss Competence Centers for Energy Research (SCCER) in addition to major activities outside Switzerland.

Transformation and innovation

The fundamental transformation of our energy system can only be a success if society and business also undergo fundamental change. This calls above all for social and economic innovations, which need to come hand in hand with technical and regulatory innovations. Bringing about societal and business change poses a huge challenge with framework conditions in constant flux. Energy efficiency alone is not enough – it has to be combined with energy sufficiency. Moreover, familiar methods and processes of innovation cannot be relied on. Several projects under NRP 70 and 71 take up this subject matter. The findings of these research projects are to be amalgamated under this key topic.

31 August 2017